

D7.1

Project website and graphical identity material

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D7.1 Project website and graphical identity material

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D7.1 Project website and graphical identity material.

Set up of the main website and portal of the MaX CoE. Identity and advertisement material ready (short and long description of the CoE, presentation slides, etc).

1. Executive Summary

The MaX website has been developed by the coordinator CNR with input for the component sections also provided by other partners. The MaX website forms a key element of the project dissemination strategy. It will be used to raise awareness of the project inside the project consortium and beyond for the purposes of community building.

The website provides an introductory suite of pages that gives an initial overview of the MaX project. It will continue to be developed as the project progresses to provide details of the project activities, outcomes and results in order to raise awareness of the project and to encourage wider adoption of the MaX solutions and promote the longer-term sustainability of the virtual research environment, training tools and services.

2. Introduction.

The deliverable D7.1 belongs to the WP7 “Building, operating, and managing the CoE communication and dissemination”.

It is part of the Task T7.5, dealing with communication activities both within CoE and towards users. The main instrument for both will be the MaX portal.

At the very beginning of MaX activities, a **communication plan** was prepared. The plan is an internal document outlining the communication strategy of the CoE, to be developed at various levels and by different subjects. The plan aims at underpinning and conveying the MaX core messages and concepts to audiences that go from the narrower community of developers to the broader society set. As in any communication plan, goals, target audience, key messages, identity tools, and communication channels have been set.

Website.

According to the above-mentioned Task T7.5, the website in this project is intended to be the main communication tool for both the internal and the external communication. (Fig. 1)

A provisional website has been set up on a Wordpress template and is on-line at <http://www.max-center.eu/>. (Additional addresses are max-project.eu and soon we will readdress the website to max-

Fig. 1 Home page of the website <http://www.max-center.eu/>

centre.eu). The template is responsive and presents a scrolling home page, while internal pages and posts are traditional. It is mainly white, a colour chosen to convey an idea of simplicity and linearity. Though the subject is quite complex and the website is full of texts and messages, the reader, at any level, is helped by a clean structure.

The website is currently addressed mostly to the external audience: additional the tools for: internal/users communication are under construction as the relevant contents are being developed.

So far the website is organized into

9 section that are expressed in the menu bar (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Menu bar of the website <http://www.max-center.eu/>

Description of sections:

The center is linked to pages “mission”, “structure” and “strategy” and gives an overview of the CoE to any kind of audience.

Materials design is linked to pages “code development”, “ecosystem & data”, “exascale enabling” and “pilot projects” and provides technical information for experts. It gives information about the core scientific aspect of the project and its main pillars.

Services is linked to pages “end-user support”, “industry” and “training and education” and is addressed to end users and stakeholders as it offers details about the aims of MaX and what it can offer to end users.

People is linked to pages “principal investigators”, “associated researchers”, and “management staff” and wants to present all the people involved and working in the project.

Events is a page that collects all events in which MaX is involved, organized within the CoE or outside it. It is continuously updated in order to track the project’s dissemination and management activities.

News is a page in which we want to collect news that belong to MaX’s world: events in MaX life, news related to MaX people or subjects (e.g., the debate about exascale transition, HPC strategies). **Links** is a page that wants to offer an overview of useful links about MaX-related topics, as, for example, the European Commission’s policy about HPC strategies. **Contacts** is the page for the management staff’s contact details. **User portal** is the link to a section, still under construction, that will offer a useful interface to users for their interaction with the CoE researchers, staff, and activities.

Fig. 3 Feature section in the homepage of the website <http://www.max-center.eu/>

The central band of the scrolling web page (Fig. 3) presents three visual links to the main features of the projects, offering information about **the center** as a whole, its aims (named “**the challenge**” to highlight the driving force of this CoE in its field), and **the crew**, to point out this CoE is made above all of expert people who want to merge their knowledge to lead the change in Europe.

MAX NEWS

Fig. 4 News section in the homepage of the website <http://www.max-center.eu/>

The lower band (Fig. 4) presents the latest **news** above MaX life as a CoE and the related world (e.g., Europe papers about HPC are collected and presented to the readers).

The footer (Fig. 5) acknowledges the European funding and gives information about the website staff.

The present website is under continuous development and all partners are asked to contribute. It will soon reach its final layout, in which news and interactions with the relevant world will be further emphasized.

The final version of the website will have an institutional section, to inform the reader on MaX whys, whos and hows, but will be centred on news and interaction with social media (such as twitter, linkedin). We believe that our communication has to be quick, updated, participated, interactive, and two-way (from/to partners, to/from users and audience), in order to become a powerful and effective tool for the CoE and have an impact on its prospective audience.

3. Visual identity.

Fig. 5 Footer of the website <http://www.max-center.eu/>

MaX developed a draft of visual identity guidelines, in order to convey its core messages to the public. These were then graphically developed by a professional communication agency (Doing, Milan) that produced a brand identity manual (December 2015).

The MaX visual identity style is simple, direct, clear and geometrical. The main features of these visual identity guidelines are:

- Colours: red, silver and white.
- Font: thin, sans-serif, geometric typeset.
- Logo: geometric and essential, conveys the idea of dynamism and open-mindedness. The red background hosts a geometrical version of the MaX word. It is accompanied by a payoff, “Driving the exascale transition”. The payoff includes MaX vision and its mission; it establishes MaX as a leading force in the transition towards exascale computing and as a centre of excellence in the world of computing. The logo is intended to be the simplest, most immediate and most recognizable representation of the MaX brand.

Fig. 6 Logo

MaX identity will be built by employing the logo in all the materials useful for communications in a coherent way. Examples are given below (letterhead, business cards, presentation slides, ...).

Fig. 7 Examples of MAX materials (business card, headed letter)

An example of related item, designed for a specific event, is the bookmark printed and distributed at SC15, the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis held in Austin, Texas, in November 2015. Its goal was to offer the main info about MaX in a synthetic and original way.

On the occasion of MaX kick-off meeting (Modena, 14/15-12-2015) a logoed notepad was prepared and distributed with the goal of introducing MaX visual identity to all participants.

All MaX-logoed materials will be made available to partners through a common online folder. The common and constant usage of these materials will be strongly recommended, in order to boost the sense of belonging within the MaX community and to make its visual identity gradually familiar to the external audience.

Fig. 8 Example of MAX materials: bookmark.

A “light” slide presentation of MaX (Fig. 9) is available on the website at the following link <http://www.max-centre.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/MaX-light-presentation.pdf>. It is useful set of slides that contains all the main info about the project; it can be used by MaX members for presentations and is at the same time an useful tool for communicating the basics about the MaX.

Fig. 9 Excerpt from the Max light presentation